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ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ В КАЗАХСТАНЕ: ПЕРЕОСМЫСЛЕНИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОДХОДОВ В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

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THE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN KAZAKHSTAN: RESHAPING PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Появление возможности использовать преимущества генеративного искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) произвело революцию в нескольких сферах, передав рутинные задачи в компетенцию машины и предоставив уникальную возможность человеку направить повышенное внимание на решение проблем. Сегодня такие передовые технологии широко используются в качестве утилиты для создания контента, где человек несет исключительную ответственность за формулирование тщательно разработанных задач, которые должны выполнять машины. Сообщества из различных сфер эффективно используют реализации ИИ (ChatGPT, Google Bard, Microsoft Copilot, Microsoft Bing AI, Perplexity) для своих повседневных рабочих задач, что дает явное преимущество, начиная от составления электронного письма и заканчивая созданием целой презентации. Используя возможности ИИ, академическое сообщество Казахстана может разрабатывать более динамичные и персонализированные схемы обучения и программы, чтобы обеспечить учащимся расширенный опыт приобретения знаний. В данной статье исследуется возможная синергия между казахстанским высшим образованием и искусственным интеллектом, подчеркивается его преобразующий потенциал. Дополнительно обсуждаются педагогические подходы для увеличения вовлеченности студентов в получении и понимании учебного материала. Исследование также содержит краткий обзор трансформации современной системы образования с точки зрения приведения в соответствие с динамично развивающимися технологиями. В конечном счете, это проливает свет на многообещающие возможности, которые вытекают из этого союза, начиная от индивидуальной разработки учебных программ и эффективной оценки и заканчивая расширенным вовлечением студентов. На стыке технологии и психологии в этой статье также рассматриваются ее глубокие последствия для тонких аспектов взаимоотношений учителя и ученика с психологической точки зрения.

ABSTRACT

The emergence of the possibility of using all the advantages of generative artificial intelligence (AI) has produced a revolution in several spheres, delegating mundane tasks to the machine's purview and giving an unique opportunity for a person to direct an increased attention on problem-solving. Today such cutting-edge technologies are extensively consumed as a content creation utility where a person is exclusively responsible for formulating elaborately designed tasks for machines to perform. Communities from various spheres have effectively utilized AI instances (ChatGPT, Google Bard, Microsoft Copilot, Microsoft Bing AI, Perplexity) for their daily work tasks, resulting in a clear advantage, ranging from composing an email to creating an entire presentation. Leveraging AI's capabilities, the academics community of Kazakhstan can design more dynamic and personalized learning curves and programmes to provide enhanced experience of knowledge acquisition by students. This paper investigates the possible synergy between Kazakhstani higher education and AI, highlighting its transformative potential. Additionally, pedagogical approaches are discussed to increase students' engagement in obtaining and understanding educational material. The investigation also provides a brief overview of the transformation of the modern education system in terms of alignment with dynamically evolving technologies. Ultimately, it illuminates the promising possibilities that arise from this union, ranging from customized curriculum development and efficient assessment to expanded student engagement. In the intersection of technology and psychology, this paper also considers its profound implications for the nuanced aspects of teacher-learner relationships from a psychological perspective.

Ключевые слова: педагогика, психология, искусственный интеллект, технологии.

Keywords: pedagogy, psychology, artificial intelligence, technology.

Introduction Reflecting on the Past

Higher education in Kazakhstan originates from the moment of formation of the Kazakh Socialist Soviet Republic. It had undergone multiple changes and reforms, which were dictated by the highest leadership of the Union. Like many countries of the former Soviet Union, Kazakhstan, being a country that was practically isolated from the outside world as part of the Soviet Union and whose fate strictly depended on the centralized apparatus in the form of the Supreme Party [9], after gaining independence in 1991 had no other choice but to inherit and adapt the outdated system of higher education in the contemporary that moment world. Kazakhstan's higher education faced great challenges in transforming the higher education paradigm that is founded on a deprecated ideology of the socialistic future.

In recent years, the landscape of higher education in Kazakhstan has witnessed a profound transformation, driven by the recognition that the conventional model, which prioritizes knowledge acquisition alone, is no longer sufficient. The rapid obsolescence of the typical knowledge model has outpaced the traditional educational cycle [15]. Consequently, the conventional approach of transferring knowledge from instructor to learner, though a cornerstone of education, has become increasingly disconnected from the dynamic realities of contemporary life.

The fundamental issue within the early republic's educational system was the insufficient comprehension of how to effectively align educational processes to ensure the acquisition of vital knowledge, which could be of great value in the post-Soviet labor market [12]. To keep the relevance of higher education for the evolving demands of the real world, a paradigm modernization became a necessity. This shift involves redefining the fundamental purpose of education, moving beyond the mere acquisition of knowledge, abilities, and skills towards the development of competencies and integral abilities for practical application. It is no longer just knowledge in isolation that holds value in the modern labor market, but rather the capacity of specialists to effectively apply their knowledge, abilities, and skills to fulfill specific functional responsibilities.

Literature review Generative Trend

The rise in popularity of generative pre-trained transformer (GPT) AI models coincided with OpenAI's decision to make its language models (ChatGPT) and user interfaces accessible to the public [1]. While these platforms continue to undergo evolution, discussions about their reliability have become commonplace across social networks, and they have also attracted the attention of academic research studies [2].

To begin with, a quick task was given to OpenAI's ChatGPT "Give a short definition for GPT". The AI returned with the following response:

"Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) is an artificial intelligence model that is pre-trained on large datasets of text and designed for natural language understanding and generation tasks.

It uses deep learning techniques to generate human-like text based on the input it receives. GPT models have been used for various language-related applications, including text generation, language translation, and question-answering." (ChatGPT, 2023).

GPT models possess a remarkable contextual understanding of language, allowing them to infer meaning from the context of the text and produce highly contextually relevant outputs. Their flexibility and adaptability have been leveraged in academic research to automate tasks such as data summarization, content generation, and language-based analysis, making them invaluable tools in various scholarly domains. The ongoing advancements in GPT models continue to refine their proficiency, opening up new possibilities for enhancing academic research and discourse [2; 4].

Methods and Materials

In this section, a comprehensive overview of the methodology employed for conducting a systematic review of the most recent literature on the intersection of artificial intelligence and higher education, with a specific emphasis on psychological aspects, is presented. The study in this scope represents a dynamic and evolving field at the forefront of contemporary educational discourse. Prioritizing recent publications guarantees that this review encompasses the most current advancements and understandings in the domain of artificial intelligence applications in higher education, particularly those associated with psychological aspects.

Augmented Workforce

The report titled "Augmented Work for an Automated, AI-driven World" by IBM presents a comprehensive exploration of the concept of the augmented workforce, emphasizing the era in which human-machine partnerships are leveraged to enhance productivity and deliver substantial business value [6]. A significant finding of the report underscores the transformative potential of operating model prioritization, indicating that organizations prioritizing their operational models as catalysts for enterprise transformation exhibit superior performance in terms of profitability, revenue growth, innovation, and employee engagement. Furthermore, the report provides valuable guidelines for selecting appropriate AI technologies, such as augmented reality (AR) or virtual reality (VR), for distinct training purposes and application domains. As a result, the report promotes the use of technology to improve the employee experience, thereby encouraging a culture of experimentation and innovation. This comprehensive report serves as a valuable resource in understanding the evolving dynamics of work, the pivotal role of technology, and the paramount significance of talent management in the contemporary, AI-driven business landscape.

The workforce augmented with artificial intelligence reinforcement is a concept that refers to the use of AI technologies to enhance the capabilities and performance of human workers. AI can augment the workforce in various ways, such as automating tasks that are time-consuming, tedious, or repetitive, and freeing up human workers to focus on more creative, complex, or strategic work; providing insights, guidance, or feedback to human workers based on data analysis, machine

learning, or natural language processing; or enhancing the skills, knowledge, or abilities of human workers through interactive learning, adaptive interfaces, or augmented reality. Harborth and Kämpers [8] explores the concept of intelligence augmentation (IA), which refers to the use of user-oriented technologies, such as AR to enhance human performance and abilities in the context of workforce training. The authors analyze the current and future situation of the German labor market, which is affected by digitalization, automation, and demographic changes. They conduct a systematic literature review of 150 papers and a practical search of 33 use cases of AR and VR applications in various occupational segments. Based on their findings, they propose a framework that provides guidelines for choosing the appropriate IA technology (AR or VR) for different training purposes and application areas.

The adoption of AI in the workplace may have positive implications for workers' transition into new roles and employability in the changing labor market. The article by Braganza et al. [3] suggests that a sophisticated AI tool that measured workers' skills and matched them to potential job roles was able to identify workers' hidden talents and suggest new career pathways that they had not considered before. The authors report that the AI tool helped workers enhance their self-efficacy, confidence and motivation, which are important factors for career development. The research paper implies that AI can support workers' decent work and well-being by providing them with personalized and tailored guidance and opportunities. Thus, the adoption of AI within the workforce carries far-reaching implications that extend beyond mere automation and have the potential to transform the nature of work, training, and career development in a rapidly evolving employment landscape.

As the study explored the profound impact of AI on workforce augmentation, it becomes evident that the evolving landscape of employment and skill development is intimately linked to the transformation of learning approaches. The following chapter introspects deeper into the educational paradigms and methodologies that are adapting to meet the challenges and opportunities presented by AI in the workplace. This transition not only signifies a shift in how individuals acquire and develop skills but also a pivotal moment in the synergy between AI technology and lifelong learning, where innovation is poised to shape the future of workforce readiness.

Shifting Learning Approaches

According to Magnusson et al. students should actively construct their own knowledge by engaging in activities that enhance their understanding or skills [14], following one of the principles of Biggs' "Constructive Alignment" model. This principle implies that learning is not a passive process of receiving information, but an active one of constructing meaning and applying knowledge. Thus, the role of the teacher is not to transmit information, but to design and facilitate learning activities that align with the intended learning outcomes. Improvement of learner's engagement into the education process requires an application of various techniques and a reconsideration of actual. The post-

soviet education model contradicts the idea that learning should not be a passive reception of information, but rather an active construction of knowledge.

Several researchers have found that learner engagement is enhanced when the learning environment presents the learning experience as an interactive "story" or "narrative" that it tells to the learner [5; 1]. Taking that findings into account, authors propose several solutions addressing the student engagement issue: 1) creation of interactive learning curves; 2) designing a curriculum in a storytelling context following a common narrative approach. Towards described proposals, the idea is to design "a suite of AI-based approaches to automatically generate learning content and add the auto-generated learning content to the learning programmes at appropriate positions" [5; 2]. It is important to note that creating content for a curriculum based on narrative approach requires a lot of time. To back this up, Kurdi et al. conducted a systematic review of several publications on common test banks and how well they work [13]. According to publications' conclusions, it was discovered that most of the questions in real exams were not good at measuring gained knowledge clearly. Diwan et al. suggest that AI could be a useful tool [5; 3]. This approach not only lowers the costs of manual creation, but also meets the demand for a constant flow of new learning materials. The narrative learning approach employs storytelling and narrations to facilitate learning across a spectrum of subjects and skills [4]. This approach is clearly delineated into various segments, within which artificial intelligence plays a pivotal role [4; 59]. Challenges confronting NLE encompass facets such as story generation, interactivity, assessment methodologies, learning outcomes, and the requisite preparation of educators. These challenges can be effectively mitigated through the integration of AI technologies. Artificial intelligence serves to enhance the narrative learning approach by furnishing interactive, technology-mediated environments where stories are collaboratively crafted by both users and the system, thereby augmenting the pedagogical utility of this approach.

Zawacki-Richter et al. present a comprehensive examination of the burgeoning landscape of AI applications within higher education [16]. This investigation involves a thorough review of 146 academic articles, elucidating AI's diverse role in higher education. Using the student life-cycle as a foundational framework, the authors outline four specific domains where AI applications demonstrate their potential: profiling and prediction, intelligent tutoring systems, assessment and evaluation, and adaptive systems and personalization. Intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) are typically crafted for individual use since "students differ on many dimensions and the goal is to be sensitive to the idiosyncrasies of individual learners" [7]. Drawing from learner models, algorithms, and neural networks, these systems have the capacity to determine the optimal learning trajectory for an individual student, select appropriate content, offer cognitive support, and facilitate meaningful dialogues to actively involve the student [16; 4]. Intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) hold significant promise, particularly within the context of large-

scale distance education institutions that administer courses with substantial enrollments, rendering one-on-one human tutoring infeasible.

In the rapidly transforming environment, it is apparent that pedagogical methodologies must urgently consider the comprehensive incorporation of technological advancements into educational schemes. Educators have to accumulate the appropriate expertise in the application of digital tools to meet the preferences of the upcoming generation of learners [10]. As a result, proposed pedagogical shifts might enhance instructors' creativity in designing discipline curriculum, thereby enhancing the appeal of the learning process.

Challenges and Future Opportunities

The infusion of AI into Kazakhstan's educational sphere presents a dual-faced challenge and opportunity. AI's introduction heralds the prospect of significantly bolstering learning outcomes. It has the potential to encourage learners to consider alternative perspectives and strategies in relation to their vocational and life paths, emphasizing its multifaceted role as a catalyst for educational and professional development [11]. This is to be achieved through the delivery of personalized, adaptive, interactive, and engaging learning experiences tailored to each learner's unique profile, encompassing needs, preferences, goals, and capabilities. In tandem with elevating learning, AI has the potential to empower educators, acting as an ally in enhancing their capabilities and performance. Teachers can expect to see a lightening of their workloads and the alleviation of professional stress. Therefore, AI aids in fostering ongoing professional development and nurturing collaboration among educators while enhancing their decision-making processes and feedback provision. The adoption of AI brings about the transformation of the educational landscape within Kazakhstan. This transformation reimagines the traditional facets of learning delivery, assessment, accreditation, quality assurance, governance, and management. The burgeoning domain of research in Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED) promises to provide educators with a more extensive array of practical guidelines and examples, while simultaneously introducing innovative pedagogical approaches. Despite prevalent skepticism, uncertainty, or concerns, AIED perseveres in presenting novel avenues for educational advancements and enhancements [17]. AI has the potential to encourage learners to consider alternative perspectives and strategies in relation to their vocational and life paths, emphasizing its multifaceted role as a catalyst for educational and professional development.

Conclusion

The rise of AI sparks a revolution across multiple sectors, automating repetitive tasks and freeing individuals to concentrate on problem-solving. Beyond educational boundaries, the introduction of AI technology carries the promise of catalyzing societal development. In the realm of higher education in Kazakhstan, AI offers the potential to craft more personalized learning programs, enhancing the student's knowledge acquisition experience. This can be witnessed through the augmentation of human capital, the strengthening of eco-

nomics competitiveness, the cultivation of social cohesion, the enrichment of cultural diversity, and the nurturing of global citizenship within the burgeoning AI-driven global landscape. The integration of AI into the education sector, therefore, emerges as a pivotal driver poised to propel both the nation and its citizens toward transformative progress.

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